

Deliverable D 7.3

IP4MaaS leaflet, version 1

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable describes and shows the first version of the Project Leaflet developed by the IP4MaaS project. In this document we describe the objectives of the leaflet, as well as the structure and design.

This first leaflet, delivered in M10, is the first out of two. A final IP4MaaS leaflet will be delivered in M20 and will focus on project pilots and results.

2 Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
CFM	Calls for Members
DL	Dissemination and exploitation leader
DoA	Description of the Action
EL	Ethical leader
EU	European Union
FS	Financial Statement
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020
IP4	Innovation Programme 4
OC	Open Call
PC	Project coordinator
PM	Project manager
PMO	Project Management Office
PMT	Project Management Team
PO	Project Officer
QAC	Quality Assurance Committee
S2R JU	Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking
TL	Technical leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work package leader

3 Background

The present document constitutes the Deliverable D7.3 “Project Leaflet First version” in the in the framework of task 7.1 of the IP4MaaS project (S2R-OC-IP4-01-2020).

4 Objective/Aim

The objectives of the IP4MaaS communication and dissemination activities are to raise awareness and disseminate project developments to key stakeholders, to ensure maximal exploitation of project results, to organise key project events, and finally to implement and update an appropriate online presence (website, social media).

The IP4MaaS Project Leaflet version 1 is an important tool to reach these goals. The leaflet has been developed to show in an instant the project objectives, scope, and partners, as well as the demo sites. It will be used to spread the word about IP4MaaS to key stakeholders through different channels, including the website, social media, but also offline means such as events.

By opting for a factsheet format, the IP4MaaS leaflet can be fully read in a relatively short amount of time, providing interested parties with the full scope of the project in an instant. In the end, the aim is to raise awareness about IP4MaaS and lead stakeholders to the project website in case they want to know more about the initiative.

The IP4MaaS leaflet can be found in Annex 1 of this document, and on the IP4MaaS website, via the link http://www.ip4maas.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/IP4MaaS-leaflet--web_final.pdf.

5 Leaflet

5.1 Design of leaflet

The leaflet has been designed by an external agency, after a careful briefing by UITP on requirements and wishes. As explained in Chapter 4, it was decided to create a leaflet in ‘factsheet’ format, so only 2 pages. This has been done to provide facts and key points about IP4MaaS in a clear, concise, and easy-to-understand way. A factsheet is easy to pick-up at events and stakeholders might be more inclined to briefly look over a two-page document than to read all pages of a multiple page brochure.

The leaflet has been designed according to the IP4MaaS visual identity, which includes specific use of colour schemes and fonts. It was decided to keep the look and feel of the leaflet clean and modern, to reflect the innovative nature of the project. This is also reflected on the leaflet’s first page (Figure 1). For the cover, an image was designed to depict a Mobility as a Service (MaaS) scheme: we see a woman holding a phone, with multiple options given to travel from A to B.

Figure 1: IP4MaaS leaflet, front page

5.2 Content of the leaflet

As we can see in Figure 1 and in Annex I, all key info on the IP4MaaS project is given on two pages. Already on the first page, the core objectives are given, as well as some key info such as the budget, timeline and number of partners. Also included are the Twitter account and website in case interested parties want to know more.

On the back page (Figure 2), we dive deeper into the IP4MaaS objectives and pilots. The six demo sites are indicated, as well as the main objectives of the project. As IP4MaaS is so closely linked with IP4, a separate text box on this is included, explaining how the project fits into the wider IP4 objectives.

OUR PARTNERS

SIX DEMOS ACROSS EUROPE

Testing multimodal travel and IP4 technologies:

BARCELONA	ATHENS	WARSAW	OSIJEK	LIBEREC	PADUA

OBJECTIVES

- 1 Design and develop a demonstration execution scheme tackling the supervision of technical integration and demonstrations' management subjects.
- 2 Monitor demonstrations of IP4 technologies in 6 different locations involving different transport operators.
- 3 Execute co-creation and collaboration activities with demonstration stakeholders for demo planning and executing, and for aligning the opinions of stakeholders on technology usage and integration.
- 4 Assess the demos to determine the success of their execution and the level of satisfaction of users with the demonstrated technologies.

IP4MAAS & IP4

The Shift2Rail (S2R) Innovation Programme 4 (IP4) aims to build a digital ecosystem for door-to-door travel in a seamless, multimodal and European-wide transport system based on the railways. IP4 is expected to radically change the way people are travelling in Europe, making railways and public transport more attractive, and addressing key societal trends such as the reduction of greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions and road congestion.

This project has received funding from the Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101015492

Figure 2: IP4MaaS leaflet back cover

6 Conclusions

By developing the project leaflet, another essential step towards a coherent and consistent project identity has been made. By following the project's visual guidelines, the brand of IP4MaaS was supported with the creation of the leaflet. Additionally, by including information in the leaflet that is free of jargon and therefore understandable for all stakeholders, the leaflet has the capacity to speak to every target audience. The leaflet also gives the readers clear guidance for those who want to know more about the IP4MaaS developments, by highlighting the project's website and Twitter account.

From its launch, the project leaflet will serve as a central tool to engage with relevant audiences and to increase interest into IP4MaaS and its mission to further support the uptake of Mobility as a Service in Europe.

7 Appendices

Annex I: IP4MaaS leaflet

IP4MaaS

THE IP4MAAS PROJECT

The IP4MaaS project aims to advance the uptake of Mobility as a Service (MaaS) schemes by analysing and testing technologies developed under the Innovation Programme 4 (IP4) of the Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking. The project's main goal is to design, execute, monitor and assess the Shift2Rail IP4 demonstrations by liaising between other projects, Transport Service Providers, and users. IP4MaaS will conduct six demonstrations in Europe testing IP4 technologies in different contexts and will deliver a solid demonstration execution scheme that can be utilised by other projects.

December 2020 - May 2023 (2,5 years)	€2.5 million	UITP (the International Association of Public Transport)	26 partners

www.ip4maas.eu @IP4MaaS_EU

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